

INCULTURATION AND LITURGICAL ADAPTATION IN THE CATHOLIC CHURCH: The Case of *Arati*

Dr. Soroj MULLICK SDB

The author <sorojmullick@gmail.com>, a Salesian priest for 33 years of Kolkata Province, has taught in college, schools, and in the formation houses. He has written a number of research papers and articles, and has 29 years of Ministry in India and abroad. He is now engaged in faith education program and animates in schools and parishes.

Abstract: This paper examines the complex question of inculturation in the Catholic liturgy in India, focusing on the ritual of *Arati* as a case study. Drawing from the Second Vatican Council's Constitution on the Sacred Liturgy (*Sacrosanctum Concilium*), subsequent magisterial documents such as *Varietates legitimae* (1994), the *Directory on Popular Piety and the Liturgy* (2001), the Catechism of the Catholic Church, and episcopal directives in India (including the "Twelve Points of Adaptation," 1969, and the CCBI directives of 2016), the study situates *Arati* within the broader theology and practice of liturgical inculturation. While proponents such as D. S. Amalorpavadass and the NBCLC argued that *Arati* could be authentically Christianized as a gesture of offering homage to Christ, critics highlight the risks of syncretism, liturgical redundancy, and semiotic ambiguity. The historical reception of *Arati* reveals both pastoral enthusiasm and persistent controversy, underscoring the importance of episcopal oversight and theological clarity. The analysis concludes that *Arati* can serve as a meaningful symbol of Indian Catholic identity if reinterpreted Christologically, carefully integrated into the liturgy, and explicitly distinguished from non-Christian ritual. This case illustrates the wider dynamics of inculturation in the Catholic Church: the creative

embodiment of faith in local cultures balanced with fidelity to the unity of the Roman Rite.

Keywords: Inculturation, *Arati*, Liturgical Adaptation, Amalorpavadass, Twelve Points of Adaptation.

INTRODUCTION

The topic of inculturation and liturgical adaptation, particularly the practice of *Arati* within Indian Catholic worship, remains a vital and unsettled question despite a widespread assumption to the contrary among many Catholic thinkers. As noted by the editor of this journal, this subject is often regarded as “settled,” yet the Jubilee Year 2025 marks a renewed call to engage with the Second Vatican Council documents, and the diverse, sometimes contrasting opinions among theologians in India, underscoring the necessity of rethinking inculturation. Inculturation must be seen as the continuous, dynamic process that integrates the Christian faith deeply into the cultural ‘soil’ of India, rather than as a mere act of ‘grafting’ or ‘transplanting’ foreign forms.¹ The persistent challenges are further reflected in the present hesitancy of many theological-liturgical institutes in India, including NBCLC – a pioneering institution in the field – to take up the issue of liturgical inculturation. They hold the position that liturgical inculturation falls under the jurisdiction of individual ritual Churches. This highlights a significant gap in official discourse and dissemination. Consequently, this author wants to make the research accessible to a wider audience of Indian Christians who must be ‘unsettled’ and engaged critically with these ongoing issues.

The question of inculturation in Catholic liturgy, particularly in India, must be examined against the Church’s magisterial tradition, which balances openness to cultural expression with fidelity to the integrity of the faith. From

¹ Cf. D. S. Amalorpavadass, *The Indian Church and Inculturation* (Bangalore: NBCLC, 1998), 45-47.

the outset, the Second Vatican Council clarified that liturgy cannot be divorced from cultural embodiment. In the *Constitution on the Sacred Liturgy*, the Council declared: “Even in the liturgy, the Church has no wish to impose a rigid uniformity in matters which do not affect the faith or the good of the whole community” (*Sacrosanctum Concilium*, no. 37). This openness acknowledges that the Church’s universal worship must be capable of assuming the symbols and gestures of local cultures. The Council further insisted: “Provided that the substantial unity of the Roman rite is preserved, provision shall be made for legitimate variations and adaptations to different groups, regions, and peoples” (SC 38). This is especially relevant for Indian Catholicism, which seeks to express faith through cultural forms such as *Arati*, a ritual offering of light traditionally performed before a deity.

Yet, Vatican II also laid down procedural safeguards:

In some places and circumstances, however, an even more radical adaptation of the liturgy is needed, and this entails greater difficulties. Therefore, the competent territorial ecclesiastical authority mentioned in Article 22, §2, must carefully and prudently consider which elements from the traditions and culture of individual peoples might appropriately be admitted into divine worship (SC 40).

Thus, while the principle of inculturation is affirmed, its application requires discernment, episcopal oversight, and ultimately Roman approval for substantial modifications.

1. SOURCES AND METHODOLOGY

With references and citations from the Second Vatican Council, the CCC, curial instructions, important Indian materials, and other recent authoritative Church documents on inculturation especially regarding liturgical worship and rituals in the Catholic Church in India, here we emphasize on the aspect of doing *Arati* as part of the process of inculturation in the Church liturgy. For each item, along with

precise reference, we note on the relevance of inculturation/ritual in India.

On a methodological note, we affirm that the magisterial teaching on inculturation emphasizes two things – (1) legitimate adaptation (*Sacrosanctum Concilium*, nos. 37-40; *Varietates legitimæ*) and (2) the need for episcopal and, where required, Roman approval for liturgical adaptations (GIRM, *Varietates legitimæ, Liturgiam authenticam*). The cited documents show that any use of *Arati* or other Indian gestures in the liturgy must be evaluated according to those principles and approved by the competent ecclesial authority (cf. SC 37-40).

2. PROGRESSIVE APPROACH TO INCULTURATION – A HISTORY

This conciliar teaching was further developed in *Varietates legitimæ* (1994), the definitive instruction on liturgical inculturation. The document gives a profound theological definition: “Inculturation signifies an intimate transformation of the authentic cultural values by their integration into Christianity and the insertion of Christianity in the various human cultures” (VL 4).² Far from being cosmetic adaptation, true inculturation is a double movement: the Gospel penetrates the culture, purifying and elevating it, while the culture enriches the Church by offering new expressions of faith. Regarding ritual gestures, *Varietates legitimæ* cautions: “Adaptations affecting gestures and postures, rites and texts, must be introduced with great circumspection and under the guidance of competent authority” (VL 48).

This caution is particularly important for rituals like *Arati*,³ which in Hindu practice are bound to notions of

² Congregation for Divine Worship and the Discipline of the Sacraments, *Varietates legitimæ: Inculturation and the Roman Liturgy* (Instruction), 25 January 1994, no. 4, in *AAS* 87 (1995): 289.

³ Cf. Mathew N. Schmalz, *The Roman Rite in Tribal North India, in Catholics & Cultures*, https://www.catholicsandcultures.org/roman-rite-tribal-north-india?utm_source=chatgpt.com (accessed on 13.09.2025). See also, Mathew N. Schmalz, “*Ad Experimentum*: Theology, Anthropology and the Paradoxes of

offering reverence to a deity. While the gesture of offering light could be seen as congruent with Christian symbolism – Christ as the Light of the World – the theological context differs significantly. As *Varietates legitimæ* notes: “In every case, care must be taken to avoid syncretism and to safeguard the substantial unity of the Roman rite” (VL 62). Thus, a ritual such as *Arati* can only be inculturated if its meaning is clearly reinterpreted in Christian terms, with explicit catechesis ensuring the faithful understand it as a sign of reverence to Christ truly present in the Eucharist.

The *Directory on Popular Piety and the Liturgy* (2001) adds another dimension by distinguishing liturgical celebrations from devotional practices. “The liturgy and popular piety, while clearly distinct, are nonetheless in a relationship of mutual enrichment and mutual fecundity” (DPPL 58).⁴ Yet the Directory warns against “the indiscriminate insertion of devotional practices into liturgical celebrations” (DPPL 59). This principle is crucial in the Indian context: while *Arati* may be a powerful expression of popular devotion, its incorporation into the Eucharist risks conflating liturgy with devotional ritual, unless carefully regulated. The Directory thus provides both a caution and an invitation: cultural forms may enrich the liturgy, but only if adapted in a way that preserves theological clarity.

Pope John Paul II provided the most authoritative magisterial synthesis of inculturation in his 1990 encyclical *Redemptoris Missio*. He defined inculturation as “the intimate transformation of authentic cultural values through their integration in Christianity and the insertion of Christianity in

Indian Catholic Inculturation,” in *Theology and the Social Sciences*, ed. Michael Barnes (Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books, 2001), 161-180.

⁴ Congregation for Divine Worship and the Discipline of the Sacraments, *Directory on Popular Piety and the Liturgy: Principles and Guidelines*, December 2001, no. 58, https://www.vatican.va/roman_curia/congregations/ccdds/documents/rc_con_ccdds_doc_20020513_vers-direttorio_en.html (accessed on 13.09.2025).

the various human cultures” (RM 52).⁵ He further clarified: “Through inculturation the Church makes the Gospel incarnate in different cultures and at the same time introduces peoples, together with their cultures, into her own community” (RM 52). For John Paul II, inculturation is not optional but integral to the Church’s mission: “A faith which does not become culture is a faith which has not been fully received, not thoroughly thought through, not faithfully lived” (RM 52, citing Paul VI).

At the same time, *Redemptoris Missio* echoed Vatican II’s caution against syncretism: “Inculturation, however, must always be guided by two principles: compatibility with the Gospel and communion with the universal Church” (RM 54). Here again, *Arati* provides a case study. If reinterpreted to symbolize offering light to Christ present in the Eucharist, and inserted into the liturgy with episcopal approval, it could embody precisely the “incarnate Gospel” John Paul II envisioned. Yet, if practiced without clear catechesis, it risks creating ambiguity about the uniqueness of Christ and the sacrificial nature of the Eucharist.

The *Catechism of the Catholic Church* provides the theological underpinning for this discussion by situating liturgy within the Incarnation itself. “The liturgy is the participation of the People of God in the ‘work of God’” (CCC 1069). As such, it is not a human invention but a divine gift. At the same time, the Catechism acknowledges the cultural mediation of this divine gift: “The liturgy is a participation in Christ’s own prayer [...] which is celebrated in the Church that is his Body in all the cultures of the world” (CCC 1073). The Catechism thus affirms that “the liturgy of the Church must involve a process of inculturation in order to remain faithful to the mystery of Christ while addressing the needs of diverse peoples” (CCC 1204, see also 1206). It explicitly states: “The liturgy of the Church presupposes,

⁵ John Paul II, *Redemptoris Missio*, 7 December 1990, no. 52, https://www.vatican.va/content/john-paul-ii/en/encyclicals/documents/hf_jp-ii_enc_07121990_redemptoris-missio.html (accessed on 13.09.2025).

integrates, and sanctifies elements from creation and human culture, conferring on them the dignity of signs of grace, of the new creation in Jesus Christ” (CCC 1149).

Taken together, these texts reveal a consistent trajectory in Catholic teaching on inculturation (see CCC on liturgy and inculturation, no. 1139). The liturgy must be embodied in the symbols and gestures of each culture, yet always in fidelity to the mystery it celebrates. For India, this means that gestures like *Arati* are not automatically excluded, but neither are they automatically permissible. Their adoption requires careful discernment, catechesis, and approval by the proper ecclesial authority. As Pope Benedict XVI later summarized, “Inculturation should be carefully considered, always keeping in mind the need to maintain the essential unity of the Roman rite” (*Sacramentum Caritatis*, no. 54).

Thus, the history of Indian Catholicism’s efforts to inculturate – beginning with the “Twelve Points of Adaptation” approved experimentally in 1969 – finds a clear framework in the magisterial tradition. The offering of light in *Arati* can indeed become a Christian sign, provided it is purified of its non-Christian connotations and reoriented to Christ, the true Light. However, its legitimacy ultimately depends not on its cultural resonance but on its theological clarity, pastoral effectiveness, and ecclesial approval. In this sense, *Arati* remains a test case of the Church’s capacity to live inculturation as both fidelity and creativity: fidelity to the one Eucharistic sacrifice of Christ and creativity in expressing that sacrifice through the gestures of India’s rich cultural heritage.

3. THEOLOGICAL DEFENSES, CRITIQUES, AND EPISCOPAL PROTOCOL FOR *ARATI* IN THE LITURGY

3.1 Theological Defenses of *Arati*

The most influential theological defense of *Arati* in the Indian Catholic liturgy comes from D. S. Amalorpavadass and the NBCLC’s movement for inculturation in the wake of Vatican II. Amalorpavadass argued that Christian liturgy in India

must not remain “culturally foreign” but should “assume, purify, and transform” local religious symbols into vehicles of Christian meaning.⁶ The *Arati*, in its Indian cultural matrix, is a gesture of reverence: offering light, flowers, or incense before a person of great dignity. According to Amalorpavadass, this symbolic action, when reinterpreted through Christian catechesis, can express *latria* – worship of Christ present in the Eucharist – without necessarily carrying Hindu doctrinal overtones.⁷

The 1969 Twelve Points of Adaptation therefore proposed that *Arati* could be introduced “at the offertory and at the conclusion of the Eucharistic prayer” as a way of offering homage to Christ present in the sacrament.⁸ The Vatican’s response (Prot. N. 802/69) granted experimental permission.⁹ For defenders of the practice, this approval legitimized the theological principle that cultural forms like *Arati* can become authentic expressions of Christian worship, provided they are inculturated through proper catechesis.

Amalorpavadass also emphasized that the liturgy should be “a locus of inculturation,” where the Gospel engages the symbols of Indian religiosity, much as early Christianity absorbed and re-signified Greco-Roman cultural elements.¹⁰ *Arati*, in his view, is not syncretism but a sacramental act of “interior transformation” whereby Christ is recognized as the true Light.

3.2 Critiques: Legal, Procedural, and Theological

The incorporation of *Arati* into the liturgy has been contested from the beginning.

⁶ D. S. Amalorpavadass, *The 12 Points of Adaptation in the Liturgy and Their Commentaries* (Bangalore: NBCLC, 1981), 14.

⁷ Cf. Amalorpavadass, *The 12 Points of Adaptation*, 18-20.

⁸ Cf. Amalorpavadass, *The 12 Points of Adaptation*, 27; see also 45.

⁹ Cf. *Consilium ad Exsequendam Constitutionem de Sacra Liturgia*, Prot. N. 802/69 (25 April 1969), in J. A. G. van Leeuwen, *Fully Indian – Authentically Christian* (Bangalore: NBCLC, 1981), appendix, 233-235.

¹⁰ Cf. Amalorpavadass, *The 12 Points*, 32, see also 67-69.

Legal and procedural critiques highlight that Prot. N. 802/69 allowed the *Arati* only on an experimental basis, not as a permanent universal adaptation.¹¹ Some critics argued that widespread adoption exceeded the Vatican's limited mandate. Furthermore, opponents alleged that the process of consultation was too narrow, with some bishops and lay groups claiming they were not sufficiently included in the discernment.

Theological critiques often focus on the risk of *syncretism*. Critics point out that *Arati* is strongly identified with Hindu worship (*puja*), where the action symbolizes offering homage to a deity. Transposing the same gesture into the Eucharist, they argue, risks confusing the faithful by importing the external forms of another religion's liturgy. As Joseph Ratzinger later warned in *The Spirit of the Liturgy*, liturgical gestures must be interpreted within the Church's Christological and Trinitarian framework, not simply transplanted from another tradition.¹² Similarly, as John Paul II warned in *Redemptoris Missio*, "Inculturation must involve the entire Christian life. It must be guided by two principles: compatibility with the Gospel and communion with the universal Church" (RM 52).

Another concern raised by theologians and canonists is the "semiotic ambiguity" of *Arati*. Even if catechesis insists that the offering of light is directed to Christ, the visual resemblance to Hindu *Puja* may blur boundaries, leading to devotional syncretism or scandal for the faithful. *The Directory on Popular Piety and Liturgy* (2001) reminds pastors that adaptations must "avoid any ambiguities or syncretism" (DPPL 118).

Finally, some liturgists argue that the Roman Rite already has rich forms of offering (incense, candles, hymns). Introducing *Arati* could create redundancy or liturgical clutter unless it is carefully integrated.

¹¹ Cf. Prot. N. 802/69, in van Leeuwen, *Fully Indian*, appendix, 234.

¹² Cf. Joseph Ratzinger, *The Spirit of the Liturgy* (San Francisco: Ignatius Press, 2000), 164.

3.3 Toward an Episcopal Protocol for *Arati* Today

Given both the theological defenses and critiques, an episcopal protocol should seek to safeguard doctrinal clarity while allowing genuine inculturation where it is pastorally fruitful. Three guidelines may be recommended:

3.3.1 Catechesis and Reinterpretation

- Bishops should mandate that *Arati* be explained to the faithful as a Christian gesture of offering homage to Christ, the true Light of the world (John 8:12). The Catechism underscores that liturgy must “integrate the particular culture of the people” but always in fidelity to Christ and the apostolic faith (CCC 1204).
- Catechesis must explicitly distinguish Christian *Arati* from Hindu ritual, emphasizing that the offering is directed solely to the Triune God, not to any created being. The Catechism of the Catholic Church cautions that “the liturgy is the participation of the People of God in the work of God,” and thus its signs must be clear and unambiguous (CCC 1069).

3.3.2 Placement in the Liturgy

- *Arati* should not replace core liturgical actions but, where permitted, may be located at the offertory (as a gesture of presenting gifts to Christ) or at the conclusion of the Eucharistic prayer (to honour Christ’s presence).¹³
- It should be performed in a sober and dignified manner, avoiding excessive dramatization or duplication of other rites (e.g., incensation).

3.3.3 Permitted Forms and Oversight

- The gesture may take the form of offering light (lamp or camphor), flowers, or incense, but should avoid

¹³ Cf. Congregation for Divine Worship and the Discipline of the Sacrament, Instruction *Redemptionis Sacramentum* (2004). https://www.vatican.va/roman_curia/congregations/ccdds/documents/rc_con_ccdds_doc_20040423_redemptionis-sacramentum_en.html?utm_source=chatgpt.com (accessed on 14.09.2025).

syncretistic symbols (e.g., *mantras* or ritual formulas from non-Christian traditions).

- Each diocese should regulate its use, ensuring it is pastorally effective and not a cause of division. Episcopal conferences (CBCI/CCBI) should provide national norms consistent with *Varietates legitimatae*, which states that adaptations must be “the fruit of a genuine liturgical inculturation” under episcopal oversight (VL 53). It states further, “The process of inculturation should maintain the substantial unity of the Roman Rite” (VL 54).

4. KUMBH ARATI

The question whether the *Arati*, especially the Hinduized *Kumbh Arati* can be performed in the Catholic liturgy, is an important and sensitive issue, because it touches on inculturation, liturgy, and interreligious sensitivity in the Catholic Church in India.

4.1 What is *Kumbh Arati*?

- In Hindu religious practice, *Arati* is a ritual offering of light (often with a lamp, camphor, or fire in a *Kumbh* vessel) accompanied by song and devotion, directed to a deity.
- In some parts of India, Catholics have used forms of *Arati*, especially with lamps, flowers, and incense, as part of inculturated worship.

4.2 Catholic Church’s General Position

- The Catholic Church encourages inculturation – adapting the Gospel to local cultures – while also ensuring that practices do not cause confusion with non-Christian worship.
- Guidelines of the Second Vatican Council (*Sacrosanctum Concilium*, nos. 37-40) allow legitimate adaptations of liturgy, provided they express the Christian faith clearly.

- Pope John Paul II (in *Ecclesia in Asia*, 1999) also encouraged inculturation, but with discernment so that “elements incompatible with the Gospel” are not introduced.

4.3 In the Indian Catholic Context

- The Catholic Bishops’ Conference of India (CBCI) and the Conference of Catholic Bishops of India (CCBI) have issued Directives on Inculturation.¹⁴
- These directives allow certain Indian cultural symbols (light, flowers, gestures of reverence, use of *deepam*) in Catholic liturgy, but with clarity that worship is directed to Christ, not to other deities.
- However, they have also cautioned against adopting explicitly ritualistic forms that have a strongly Hindu theological meaning, such as offerings with *Kumbh* or actions that may imply polytheistic devotion.

4.4 Specifically about *Kumbh Arati*

The questions remain: Can the Catholics offer *Kumbh Arati*?

The answer is:

- Yes: Catholics may use a form of *Arati* (lamp offering, singing, reverent gestures) as an inculturated expression of praise to Christ, Mary, or the saints.
- No: A *Kumbh Arati* in its original Hindu sense (rituals associated with purification, deities, or the *Kumbh Mela*) cannot be directly transplanted into Catholic liturgy, because it carries strong religious meanings that may blur Christian identity.
- The CCBI 2016 *Directives for the Celebration of the Liturgy* (Ch. VIII, 2, pp. 41-42) note that *Arati* may be permitted in certain contexts, but it should be simplified, Christ-centered, and stripped of theological connotations alien to Christianity.

¹⁴ Cf. CCBI, *Directives for the Celebration of the Liturgy* (Bangalore: CCBI Commission for Liturgy, 2016), Ch. VIII, 2, pp. 41-42.

4.5 Pastoral Guidelines

If Catholics perform an *Arati* (lamp waving, singing), it should:

- Be clearly directed to Christ or the Eucharist.
- Use Christian hymns or psalms, not mantras.
- Avoid ritual forms that imitate Hindu deity worship (like *Kumbh* with water for purification).

It is best performed in devotional gatherings (Marian feasts, Eucharistic adoration) rather than inside the central Eucharistic Liturgy, unless specifically approved by the bishops.

Thus, according to the official document titled “*Directives for the Celebration of the Liturgy 2016*” with a published text on *Arati* by CCBI, Catholics in India may use a Christianized form of *Arati* (lamp offering, hymns) as inculturated devotion. But a direct *Kumbh Arati* as in Hindu worship is not permitted, since it risks confusion and theological ambiguity. What is allowed is a purified, Christ-centered adaptation, under episcopal guidelines. The “12 Points of Adaptation” approved in 1969 (CBCI + NBCLC) include as one of the points: “In the Offertory rite, and at the conclusion of the Anaphora the Indian form of worship may be integrated, that is, double or triple ‘*Arati*’ of flowers, and/or incense and/or light.”¹⁵ A recent academic article (2024) says that in those 12 points, “frequent use of the traditional Indian rite of *Arati* (i.e., the circular waving of a lamp in homage)” is among the external liturgical adaptations suggested.¹⁶

¹⁵ Cf. Ephesians-511.Net, *The Arati in the Liturgy – Indian or Hindu?*, April 22, 2015, https://ephesians511blog.com/2015/04/22/the-arati-in-the-liturgy-indian-or-hindu/?utm_source=chatgpt.com (accessed on 13.09.2025).

¹⁶ Cf. Zdenek Stipl, “Achievements of Inculturation in the Indian Catholic Church,” *Studia Orientalia Slovaca* 23/2 (2024): 69-98, https://www.academia.edu/126863812/Achievements_of_Inculturation_in_the_Indian_Catholic_Church_Studia_Orientalia_Slovaca_23_2024_2_pp_69_98?utm_source=chatgpt.com (accessed on 16.09.2025).

5. THE IMPLICATION OF THE TWELVE POINTS ON INCULTURATION

As we have already mentioned, the historical context of the ritual of *Arati* itself is discussed within the framework of the “Twelve Points on Inculturation,” developed by the Catholic Bishops of India in 1969, which remains a landmark document guiding the balance between cultural adaptation and doctrinal fidelity.¹⁷ These points emphasize the importance of discerning adaptations that respect the theological integrity of Catholic worship while recognizing the richness of Indian cultural symbols. *Arati*, a light-offering ritual traditionally performed before Hindu deities, has been reinterpreted in Indian Catholicism as a gesture of homage to Christ, a process championed by scholars and pastoral leaders such as D. S. Amalorpavadass.¹⁸ This reinterpretation illustrates the tensions and possibilities inherent in inculturation: preserving the unity of the Roman Rite while creatively engaging with the cultural expressions of faith unique to India.

These “Twelve Points” emerged from the liturgical renewal set in motion by Vatican II, shaped decisively by the All-India Liturgical Meeting of January 1969 under the auspices of the CBCI’s liturgy commission and the then newly founded National Biblical, Catechetical and Liturgical Centre (NBCLC) in Bangalore, with D. S. Amalorpavadass as its leading architect.¹⁹ The published compilations and commentaries assembled by NBCLC, edited and later published by him, provide the canonical presentation of the twelve proposals and their pastoral rationale, which became the standard source for parish implementation

¹⁷ Cf. Catholic Bishops’ Conference of India, *Twelve Points on Inculturation* (Bangalore: CCBI Press, 1969), 5-9.

¹⁸ Cf. Amalorpavadass, *The Indian Church and Inculturation*, 52-54.

¹⁹ Cf. D. S. Amalorpavadass, *Adaptation and Inculturation: The Indian Experience* (Bangalore: NBCLC, 1971), 14-18.

and catechetical orientation in the 1970s and 1980s.²⁰ The bishops' commission submitted to the Consilium (the Vatican body responsible for implementing *Sacrosanctum Concilium*) a set of concrete proposals, which were granted official experimental approval in Prot. N. 802/69 (25 April 1969).²¹

This Vatican letter authorized the Indian Church to implement twelve specific adaptations on a provisional basis: (i) sitting on the floor or standing in local postures with footwear removed; (ii) replacing genuflections with the *anjali hasta*; (iii) incorporating the *panchanga pranam* before the Liturgy of the Word, at the penitential rite, and following the anaphora; (iv) adapting the kissing of objects to Indian custom (touching and raising hands to eyes or forehead); (v) giving the sign of peace through the *anjali hasta* or enclosing the hands of the other; (vi) using a simple incense bowl; (vii) adopting a single tunic-style chasuble with stole (*angavastra*); (viii) substituting the corporal with a tray (*thali* or *thamboola thattu*); (ix) replacing candles with oil lamps; (x) including in the entrance rite a celebrant's welcome with a single *arati*, hand-washing, lamp-lighting, and mutual greetings of peace; (xi) permitting spontaneity in the prayers of the faithful while maintaining universality; and (xii) integrating Indian forms of worship such as double or triple *arati* of flowers, incense, or light at the offertory and after the anaphora.²²

Among these, the inclusion of *arati* – later singled out for controversy – became emblematic of the wider debate

²⁰ Cf. Jon Douglas Anderson, *Sacrosanctum Concilium and Inculturation of Liturgy in the Post-Conciliar Indian Catholic Church*, https://www.academia.edu/287582/Sacrosanctum_Concilium_and_Inculturation_of_Liturgy_in_the_Post_Conciliar_Indian_Catholic_Church?utm_source=chatgpt.com (accessed on 13.09.2025).

²¹ Cf. Vatican Congregation for Divine Worship, Letter to the CBCI, Prot. N. 802/69, April 25, 1969 (Vatican Archives; unpublished).

²² Cf. CBCI, *Theological Advisory Commission and Liturgy Commission: Approved Adaptations for India* (Bangalore: NBCLC Documentation Service, 1969), 3-7.

over the limits of liturgical inculturation.²³ While the Vatican response permitted experimentation, the reception in India was contested, with some bishops and theologians (not least Amalorpavadass and his circle at NBCLC) advocating creative fidelity, while others expressed caution over syncretism and ritual excess.²⁴ The CCBI archives and Amalorpavadass's writings provide the primary record of this exchange, together with the Vatican's correspondence.²⁵ Subsequent clarifications, particularly the 1994 instruction *Varietates legitimae* and the 2001 *Directory on Popular Piety*, reframed the question of legitimate adaptation, underscoring both the pastoral need for rootedness in culture and the doctrinal limits to innovation.²⁶ Later scholarship has presented divergent interpretations, some affirming the bold theological vision of the "Twelve Points" and others warning of their problematic reception, making this episode a continuing reference point in debates on inculturation in India.²⁷

One of the most contested items – often cited as Point 12 in secondary summaries – reads, in effect, that in the Offertory and at the conclusion of the anaphora "the Indian form of worship may be integrated," specifying possibilities such as a double or triple *Arati* (flowers, incense and/or light). The twelfth Point of the adaptation reads: "In the Offertory rite, and at the conclusion of the Anaphora the Indian form

²³ Cf. D. S. Amalorpavadass, "The Indian Rite: Problems and Perspectives," *Journal of Dharma* 2/4 (1977): 367-370.

²⁴ Cf. Amalorpavadass, *Adaptation and Inculturation*, 22-26; cf. George Nedungatt, "Inculturation in India: An Appraisal," *VJTR* 46 (1982): 115-118.

²⁵ Cf. Catholic Bishops' Conference of India (CBCI), *Documents on Liturgy: 1969-1975* (New Delhi: CBCI Centre, 1976), 55-63.

²⁶ Cf. Congregation for Divine Worship and the Discipline of the Sacraments, *Varietates legitimae: Fourth Instruction for the Right Application of the Conciliar Constitution on the Liturgy* (January 25, 1994), §§ 48-53; idem, *Directory on Popular Piety and the Liturgy* (December 2001), §§ 91-95.

²⁷ Cf. Thomas Kolarczyk, "Indian Inculturation and the Arati Controversy," in *Inculturation and the Liturgy in Asia*, ed. Anscar J. Chupungco (Quezon City: Claretian Publications, 2002), 201-207.

of worship may be integrated, that is, double or triple ‘arati’ of flowers, and/or incense and/or light.” This clause (and related proposals: *anjali*/hands-joined gestures, removal of shoes, use of Indian postures, Indian music/dance) made the Twelve Points the *locus classicus* for debates about the limits of liturgical inculturation in India.²⁸

5.1 Rome’s Reaction and Canonical Status

The documentary reply Prot. N. 802/69 (signed at the Consilium and addressed to the CBCI commission) effectively allowed experimental trials of the proposed adaptations, but it was not a blanket, permanent approbation for a new “Indian Rite.” The Consilium’s communication is preserved in the archival record reproduced and discussed in studies such as J. van Leeuwen’s *Fully Indian – Authentically Christian* and related NBCLC publications; scholars who have worked the archive emphasize that the permission was experimental and conditioned on careful local supervision and continuing reporting to Rome.²⁹

That experimental permission did not end the controversy. Many critics (both inside India and internationally) argued that the adaptations – especially gestures and rites with strong Hindu connotations – risked syncretism or misled the faithful; others defended them as authentic inculturation consonant with *Sacrosanctum Concilium*. Academic and journalistic accounts record a mixed reception: the adaptations were enthusiastically taken up in many dioceses and at NBCLC-led formation centres, while other bishops, priests, and lay groups resisted and complained against them. The Catholic press and regional reviews recorded both the spread of experimental “Indianized” liturgies and repeated complaints that some practices had exceeded the intent of the experimental permission.³⁰

²⁸ Cf. Ephesians-511.Net, *The Arati in the Liturgy*.

²⁹ Cf. van Leeuwen, *Fully Indian - Authentically Christian*,

³⁰ Cf. *Biblical, Catechetical, Liturgy Center Renews Church*, NBCLC, UCANews,

5.2 Reception in India: Pastoral Adoption and Public Controversy

Within India, the practical uptake was substantial in some regions. NBCLC resources, diocesan liturgy workshops, and catechetical programs promoted the Twelve Points as a way to make the Mass intelligible and culturally resonant. Amalorpavadass – the most public theological advocate – framed the proposals as part of a genuine “inculturation” movement that sought an “interior transformation” of Indian cultural symbols by Christian meaning. Many parishes incorporated selected items (incense, local music, gestures such as *anjali*), and some communities did experiment with *Arati* in offertory or post-communion devotional moments.³¹

At the same time, conservative critics (and a number of litigants and lay groups) argued the 12-point program constituted an improper “Hinduization” of the liturgy and accused parts of the ecclesial leadership of procedural shortcuts in how the Vatican permission was obtained; polemical tracts and strongly worded pamphlets circulated widely and keep resurfacing in online archives and blogs. Scholars note that this controversy shaped a long-lasting polarization in Indian liturgical practice: enduring experimentation in some places and retrenchment or repudiation in others.³²

5.3 Aftermath and Later Magisterial Framing

Two further developments are important. First, over the following decades the Vatican’s liturgical dicastery and subsequent instructions (notably *Varietates legitimae*

July 26, 1992, https://www.ucanews.com/story-archive/?post_id=300&post_name=%2F1992%2F07%2F27%2Fbiblical-catechetical-liturgy-center-renews-church&utm_source=chatgpt.com (accessed on 13.09.2025).

³¹ Cf. Douglas Anderson, *Sacrosanctum Concilium and Inculturation of Liturgy*,

³² Cf. Ephesians-511.Net, *The Paganized Catholic Church in India – By Victor J. F. Kulanday*, 1985, December 4, 2013, https://ephesians511blog.com/2013/12/04/the-paganized-catholic-church-in-india-by-victor-j-f-kulanday-1985-2/?utm_source=chatgpt.com (accessed on 13.09.2025).

[1994] and the *Directory on Popular Piety and the Liturgy* [2001]) placed stronger emphasis on procedures, theological safeguards, and episcopal responsibility for adaptations—reiterating that gestures or rites may be adopted only with careful theological re-interpretation and proper ecclesial approvals. Second, Indian episcopal bodies (CBCI/CCBI and NBCLC) continued to provide pastoral orientations but were repeatedly reminded that an experimental permission does not equate to perpetual, universal license. In practice that meant some local usages continued pastorally where bishops judged them pastorally appropriate and the meaning clearly Christianized; elsewhere bishops suppressed or limited controversial elements.³³

6. SNAPSHOT TAKEAWAYS

Here is the summary of both the main theological defenses (Amalorpavadass) and the main critiques (legal/procedural and theological), providing recommended language for an episcopal protocol for *Arati* today (catechesis, placement in the liturgy, permitted forms).

Historically, the Twelve Points (Prot. N. 802/69, 25 Apr 1969) mark the clearest institutional opening for liturgical experiments in India and include the explicit proposal that *Arati* could be used in certain offertory/anaphoral contexts. However, that opening was expressly experimental and has been the subject of sustained debate: scholarly defenders (Amalorpavadass and NBCLC) treat it as authentic inculturation; critics see it as overreach or even syncretism. Subsequent magisterial norms have tightened procedural and theological guardrails, so the canonical and pastoral legitimacy of *Arati* in the Mass now depends on careful theological reinterpretation, episcopal oversight, and conformity with the norms the Church later articulated.³⁴

³³ Cf. van Leeuwen, *Fully Indian - Authentically Christian* (Bangalore: NBCLC, 1981).

³⁴ Cf. Jon Douglas Anderson, *Sacrosanctum Concilium and Inculturation of Liturgy in the Post-Conciliar Indian Catholic Church*; van Leeuwen, *Fully*

In its treatment of inculturation, the CCBI recalls the Twelve Points, noting that these are not obligatory but optional, to be adopted wholly or in part to foster an Indian atmosphere in worship.³⁵ The Catholic Church has consistently emphasized that the liturgy, while universal in essence, must be able to “take root” in diverse cultures through careful and faithful adaptation.

CONCLUSION

In sum, the question of *Arati* in the Catholic liturgy demonstrates both the richness and the tension of inculturation in India. On one hand, it reveals the genuine pastoral desire to root Christian worship in the cultural soil of the people, echoing the conciliar principle that “the Church has no wish to impose a rigid uniformity” (SC 37). On the other hand, it underscores the theological and canonical need for discernment, since symbols drawn from non-Christian traditions carry powerful connotations that cannot be uncritically transferred into Catholic worship.

This above debate and argument over *Arati* in the liturgy encapsulate the promise and peril of inculturation in India. Amalorpavadass’ vision highlights the potential of indigenous symbols to enrich Christian worship, while the critiques caution against theological ambiguity and canonical overreach. A balanced episcopal protocol – grounded in catechesis, clear placement, and regulated forms – can allow *Arati* to serve as an authentically Indian expression of Catholic worship without diluting the integrity of the Roman Rite (cf. RM 52).

Indian - Authentically Christian. For a careful historical primary source base, consult Amalorpavadass’s NBCLC collection (The Twelve Points, 1981), the Consilium letter Prot. N. 802/69 reproduced in archived studies (van Leeuwen et al.), and the CBCI/CCBI documentation and liturgical resources.

³⁵ On general liturgical decorum and local inculturation, cf. CCBI, *Directives for the Celebration of the Liturgy* (84 pages; CCBI, 2016), Ch. VI, “The Question of Inculturation,” 35-36.

The history of the “Twelve Points of Adaptation” and the subsequent magisterial guidance make clear that inculturation is not a matter of arbitrary creativity but of faithful reinterpretation, ecclesial oversight, and fidelity to the Gospel. *Arati*, when purified and reoriented toward Christ as the Light of the World, can indeed enrich the liturgy as a culturally resonant gesture of homage. Yet without catechesis and episcopal regulation, it risks confusion, syncretism, and liturgical clutter.

Ultimately, the case of *Arati* shows that inculturation is not merely about external forms but also about the deeper theological task of allowing the Gospel to transform cultures from within. As John Paul II reminded, “a faith which does not become culture is a faith which has not been fully received” (RM 52). In this sense, the careful discernment of *Arati*’s place in Indian Catholic worship remains a test of the Church’s ability to live inculturation as both fidelity and creativity: fidelity to the Eucharistic mystery and creativity in expressing it through the living symbols of India’s rich cultural heritage.

An excerpt taken from Pope Leo XIV’s Encyclical *Magnifica Humanitas* (2026), no. 211.

“Christians see the darkness and acknowledge it for what it is, yet they do not merely gaze upon it passively, for they know the light and understand that the darkness has not overcome it and cannot defeat it (cf. Jn 1:5). For this reason, even when suffering seems to have the last word, Christians serve the good and are sustained by a theological hope that gives reality both meaning and direction.”